

7. GANDHARVAPURI, AN IMPORTANT CENTRE OF PARAMARA ART

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The village of Gandharvpuri, now known as Gandhawal, is located 10 Km north-east of Sonkatch, *tehsil* headquarter in Dewas district of Madhya Pradesh, situated on Bhopal-Indore road.

Gandharvpuri is a prolific site of Hindu and Jaina images of artistic merit belonging to the medieval period. It has yielded a large number of images of Paramāra period. These images are lying scattered in and around the village. Recently the Government of Madhya Pradesh has collected some of these images and kept them in an open air museum established at the site.

Gandharvpuri has also yielded remains of some temples of the Paramāra period. The following temples deserve mention :-

1. Temples of Gandharvasena datable to C.11th-12th Centuries A.D.
2. Two Jaina temples in a group, datable to C.11-12th centuries A.D.
3. The modern temple of Śītalāmātā with sculptures of C.11-12th centuries A.D. fixed in its doorway.

Besides these temples, there is a tomb called Dargah inside the village. Architectural fragments of temples belonging to C.11-12th centuries A.D. have been used in the construction of the platform of this tomb. An inscribed memorial pillar and an inscribed satīstone mentioning the name of *sati* as *Hemlatā* have also been noticed at the site.

A number of architectural fragments of ruined temples have been used in the construction of houses and temples in the village. The modern temples of Rāma, Kheḍāpati and Bhavānī, located in and around the village, have many sculptural and architectural fragments of medieval temples fixed in their platforms or walls. Some of the medieval sculptures are kept loose inside the village on platforms and are in worship.

The present paper briefly describes the ancient Hindu and Jaina remains at Gandharvpuri and discusses their significance.

Hindu remains

Temple of Gandharvasena or Sivalaya :-

The temple of Gandharvasena, (Fig. 1-2) is dedicated to Śiva. It consists on plan of a sanctum crowned by a *sikhara* and is datable to C.11th cen.A.D. It is built of sandstone and faces east. Of the original temple, only the basement mouldings have survived. The structure above the mouldings is modern.

The sanctum is *pancharatha* on plan. The niches on the *bhadras* of the sanctum are lying vacant. On the lintel of the sanctum door-way are depicted nine images of Śiva each seated in *lalitasana*. The sanctum enshrines a Śivaliṅga and a seated Nandī.

The following images are fixed in the niches inside the sanctum:

1. Four-armed Pārvatī standing in *samabhanga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamala, sruk, sarpa* and *ghata*. She wears a *jatamukuta* on her head. Seated Kārttikeya and Gaṇeśa are shown on the right and left of her head respectively
2. A modern image of a four-armed deity having the head of a donkey. It stands in *samabhanga*. The local people call this image as that of Gandharvasena, who according to them, ruled over this territory during ancient times and after whom the village is known as Gandharvpurī.

The following images are fixed on the exterior walls of the sanctum on the front or eastern side.

1. Four-armed Vāmana standing in *samabhanga*. and carrying broken, *chakra* and *sankha* The circular halo behind his head is decorated with lotus petals. The halo is flanked on the right by four-armed seated Brahmā and on the left by four-armed seated Śiva. On the top of the halo is depicted a lotus.
2. Four-armed Śani seated in *lalitā sana* on his mount buffalo. He carries *abhaya, danda, pasa* and a manuscript and wears a *jatamukuta*. There is a circular halo behind his head.

Images fixed on the walls of the antarala (vestibule)

1. Four-armed seated Gaṇeśa carrying *abhaya-cum-padma, parasu*, indistinct and a *modakapatra*.
2. Four-armed Vishnu standing in *sambhanga* and carrying broken, *gada, chakra* and

sankha. He wears an elongated *kiritamukuta* and *vanamala*.

Loose architectural and sculptural fragments kept in the compound of the temple :

1. Bracket of a pillar carved with four *kichakas* on four faces. It is made of white sandstone and is datable to C.11th cen. A.D.
2. Six stone ceiling slabs each carved with a *nābhichhanda* design having *kola* and *gajatalu* courses. They are made of white sandstone and are datable to C.11th cen. A.D.
3. Thirteen fragmentary pillars each carved with foliage design and datable to C.11th cen. A.D.
4. A bearded ascetic seated in *anjalinudra*. His head is flanked on either side by a flying *vidyadhara* holding a garland. The left leg of the ascetic and the garland held by the *vidyadhara* on his left are broken. It is datable to C.11th cen. A.D.
5. A *sati*-stone pillar bearing an inscription in Devanāgarī characters of C. 11th cen. A.D.
6. A number of stone lintels each carved with lotus-petals and *tamalpatras*. They are datable to C.11th cen. A.D.

2. *Khedapati temple :*

The Khedapati temple is a modern one. It consists on plan of an oblong sanctum alone. The following ancient sculptures datable to C.11th cen. A.D. are fixed on a platform in the sanctum.

1. Umā-Maheśvara seated on the bull. The image is much weather-worn.
2. A fragmentary *Navagraha* panel showing six of the nine standing *grahas*. These *grahas* are Budha, Bṛihaspati, Śukra, Śani, Rāhu and Ketu.
3. Seated Umā-Maheśvara. The mounts bull and lion are shown below.
4. Seated Gaṇeśa.
5. Hanumān in *pratyālīdha* pose, Below his right leg is seen a mutilated kneeling demon figure.
6. Three *Yonipattas*.

On the right of this temple is lying an image of Mahishamardinī Durgā. She is *eight-armed* and carries *trisula* piercing through the neck of the buffalo demon, *khadga*, *khetaka*, *ghanta* and holding the hair of the demon. The mount lion is attacking the buffalo demon from behind. It is made of white sand-stone and is datable to C.11th century A.D.

In front of the Khedāpati temple is seen a sati-stone pillar bearing an inscription in devanāgarī characters of C.11th century A.D.

3. *Sitalamata temple* :

The Śītalāmātā temple inside the village consists of a high masonry platform on which are fixed the following sculptures datable to C.11th Century A.D.

1. Four-armed seated Viṣṇu.
2. Śeṣhaśāyī Viṣṇu.
3. Four-armed Pārvatī standing in *samabhanga* and carrying broken, lotus-stalk with seated Kartikeya, lotus-stalk with seated Gaṇeśa and kalasa. Her head is lost.
4. A *vyala*.
5. A *dvarapala* holding a long staff in his right hand.
6. Four-armed Pārvatī with all hands broken. She held a *sruk* in her upper right hand.
7. A *vyala* figure.
8. Fragment of a lintel depicting a four-armed standing male deity in a niche. Three seated deities are shown to his left.
9. An *Apsaras* standing in a niche. Both her hands are lost. A female is shown standing on her right.
10. Mahishamardini Durga. The image is weather-worn.
11. A marching elephant.
12. Four-armed standing Hari-Hara carrying broken, broken, *chakra* and broken. On the right half of his head he wears a *jatamukuta* and on the left half a *kiritamukuta*.
13. Four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitasana* with his consort.
14. Āsavapāyī Kubera seated in *lalitasana*. He is two-armed and carries a wine-cup and a long purse (*nakulaka*). He wears a *kaṇḍamukuta*. The circular halo behind his

head is flanked on either side by a flying *vidyadhara* carrying a garland. A female standing on his right is shown pouring wine in his cup.

15. An *apsaras* standing in a niche.
16. Three-headed and four-armed Brahmā standing in *samabhanga*.
17. Four-armed and three-headed Vaikuntha Vishnu riding on Garuda. The three heads from left to right are those of lion, man and bear. On the right of his head is shown seated four-armed Brahmā and on the left is portrayed seated four-armed Śiva.
18. An *apsaras* standing in a niche and holding a lotus in her left hand.
19. A stone slab carved with a serpent.
20. An *apsaras* standing.
21. An *apsaras* standing in a niche.
22. An *apsaras* standing.
23. Five-headed Śiva standing in *samabhanga*. He wears a *jatamukuta*. On the right of his head is depicted seated Brahma and on the left is shown seated Vishṇu.
24. Vishṇu riding on Garuda.
25. A two-armed *Saiva dvarapala* with fan-shaped headdress, carrying sword and shield.
26. A standing *Saiva dvarapala*.
27. A standing *Saiva dvarapala*.
28. A standing *Saiva dvarapala*.
29. Four-armed and three-headed male deity seated in *padmasana*, both upper hands have been mutilated.
30. A *Vyala*.
31. An *apsaras* standing in a niche and looking into a mirror held in her left hand.
32. An *apsaras* standing.
33. Four-armed Pārvatī standing in *sambhanga*. She wears an elongated *jatamukuta* and carries a *pustaka* and a *padma* in her upper right and left hand respectively.

34. Four-armed Pārvatī standing in *sambhanga*. and carrying *abhaya-cum-akshamala*, lotus-stalk, *vina* and *kalasa*. She wears a *jatamukuta*.
35. Four-armed Pārvatī standing in *sambhanga* on a lotus. She carries *varada-cum-akshamala* in her only surviving lower right hand.

3. Bhavani Temple

Bhavānī temple is a modern structure with old door jambs datable to C.11th century A.D.

The right jamb is decorated with four *sakhas*. The first *sakha* depicts diamonds and rosettes, the second *sakha* depicts flying Gandharvas playing on musical instruments and flying Vidyādharas holding garlands. The third *sakha* portrays four panels arranged one above the other, each depicting four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitasana*. The fourth *sakha* is carved with *vyalas*. The lower portion of this flank depicts a four-armed *Saiva-dvarapala* standing in *tribhanga* in a niche which is flanked on either side by Ganga and Yamuna.

The door jamb on the left is carved with three *sakhas*. The first *sakha* depicts diamonds and rosettes, the second portrays flying Gandharva couples playing on musical instruments, and the third depicts three panels, arranged one above the other, each showing a four-armed *Devi* seated in *lalitasana*. The lower portion of this flank is decorated with three figures each standing in *tribhanga*. These figures are from left to right (1) a female holding a *kalasa* by both her hands (2) a female playing on *vina* held by both her hands and (3) a male *dvarapala*.

The door-sill of the temple also belongs to a Hindu temple of C.11th century A.D. It is carved in the centre with a *mandaraka* flanked on either side by a dance and music panel. In front of the door-still is seen *chandrasila* carved with a conch on either end.

4. Rama Mandira

The Rāma Mandira outside the village is a modern temple dedicated to lore Rāma. In the front facade of this temple are seen the following sculptures and architectural members.

1. Fragmentary stone carved with a niche containing an image of Kubera seated in *lalitasana* and carrying *matulunga*, *gada*, *sarpa* and *nakulaka* (purse).
2. *Chandrasila* carved with half-lotus design.

5. Rama Mandira:

Rāma mandira inside the village is a modern structure with a door-frame and *chandrasila* of

C.11th century A.D. In front of the temple is a tamarind tree under which is kept a stone sculpture of four-armed dancing Gaṇeśa datable to C.11th cen. A.D. On the left of Gaṇeśa is shown a male-drummer.

Hindu sculptures lying on the bank of river Somavati on the outskirts of the village

Two-armed Sūrya standing in *samabhanga* in a niche composed of two pilasters. The image is made of white sandstone and is datable to C.11th century A.D.

6. *Rama Mandira on the Bank of River Somavati :*

Rama Mandira on the bank of river Somavatī is a modern structure. The following stone sculptures are seen on the platform of this temple. The sculptures are datable to C. 11th century A.D.

1. A *yonipatta* lying loose.
2. A frieze depicting protruding elephant-heads and flying *vidyadharas* carrying garlands. It is fixed on the platform.
3. A stone-slab carved with an image of four-armed Vishṇu riding on Garuda and carrying broken, *gada*, *chakra* and broken. He wears a *kiritamukuta*.

Besides, ten fragmentary pillars decorated with various designs such as *grasapatti* and foliage are also lying near the temple.

Hindu Sculptures and Architectural fragments used in the construction of the Tomb or Dargah :

A number of stone-slabs of the Hindu temples datable to C.11th century A.D. have been used in the construction of the platform of the Dargah inside the village. Some of these slabs are carved with palm-leaf design.

On the north of the tomb is another platform with architectural fragments of C.11th Century A.D. fixed into it. These architectural fragments are (1) a fragmentary pillar carved with two decorative bands and a ribbed padma. (2) a stone-slab carved with palm-leaf design (3) a fragmentary pillar decorated with a frieze of *kirttimukhas* and *chaitya*-arches (4) and lintel of a temple doorway.

There is also a *sati*-stone pillar bearing an inscription in *devanagari* characters of C.11th century A.D. It depicts (A) a male warrior riding a horse and going to the battle-field (B) the

male warrior lying and his consort flying (C) worship of the Śivalinga by the *sati* in the heavens (D) Sūrya and chandra.

The bust of a male deity is fixed in the platform of the tomb.

Architectural fragments of Hindu temples lying in Muslim Graveyard inside the village:

A number of architectural fragments of Hindu temples are lying in the Graveyard in the village. The following may be noted:

1. A fragmentary pillar decorated with a frieze of *kirttimukhas*.
2. A stone-slab decorated with a diamond design in a panel.
3. A door-still of a temple. It is carved in the centre, with a *mandaraka* flanked on the left by two standing female figures, a male playing on *vina* and a male dancing.
4. Basement of a pillar carved with a vase-and-foilage design.
5. A fragmentary pillar decorated with a band of *kirttimukhas*.

Hindu sculptures and architectural fragments fixed or lying loose in private houses in the village :

A number of sculptural and architectural fragments are lying loose or fixed in private houses in the village.

In front of the Rāma Mandira near the market is a peepal tree under which is kept a loose sculpture of Varāha. Varāha is four-armed and stands in *pratyaldha*. He holds *kati*, broken, *chakra* and broken. He stands under a lotus-parasol. The goddess Pṛithvī is seen seated on his left elbow. His left foot is placed on the head of the demon killing Hiranyāksha shown in *anjalmudra*. He is flanked on either side by a standing attendant.

A stone-slab depicting Dikpāla Indra on one facet and Dikpāla Agni on the other facet is fixed in the platform in front of the house of Hari Mahārāja in the Thana locality of the village. On the left of Indra is shown his mount elephant. Flames are seen issuing from the head of Agni. These images are partly mutilated.

On a platform in the *bada* of Rama Sinha are lying the following sculptural fragments datable to C.11 century A.D.

1. Head of a male-deity wearing *karandamukuta* and *kundalas* .

2. A stone-slab carved with a four-armed male deity seated in *lalitasana*. A flying vidyādhara holding a garland is shown on his left near the head.

Hindu sculptures and architectural members in the open air museum:

(Plate ?, Fig. 3) The following sculptural and architectural members are lying in the open air museum:-

1. Cruciform bracket carved with a flying *bhuta* on each facet.
2. A fragmentary pillar decorated with foliage, diamonds and rosettes.
3. A stone-slab carved with *apsaras* holding lotus-stalk in her right hand. To her left is shown a flying *vidyadhara*.
4. A stone-slab engraved with a niche containing an image of two-armed Sūrya standing in *samabhanga* and holding lotuses in both hands.
5. An *apsaras* standing in *tribhanga* in a niche.
6. A stone-slab decorated with diamonds and rosettes, a flying *vidyadhara* couple and a niche containing an image of a four-armed male deity seated in *lalitasana*.
7. An *apsaras* standing in a niche.
8. Four-armed Śiva seated in *lalitasana*. and playing on *vina*. He carries shaft of *vina*, *damaru*, shaft of *vina* and *trisula*.
9. A Śivalinga.
10. A seated mutilated Nandī wearing a chain of bells.
11. Bust of Sūrya standing in a niche and holding lotuses in both hands.
12. A niche containing an image of four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitasana*, and carrying *abhaya*, *parasu*, *parasu* and *modakapatra*.
13. A seated crocodile.
14. A four-headed and eight-armed image of Hari-Hara-Hiranyagarbha (Plate ?, Fig. 4) standing in *samabhanga* and carrying *varada*, chopped off, *trisula*, *padma*, *padma*, *khatvanga*, *chakra* and *kalasa*. There is a circular halo behind his head. This image is a composite image representing a combination of Brahmā, Viṣṇu, Śiva and Sūrya. The head of Brahmā is bearded and wears a *jatamukuta*. The heads of Viṣṇu and Sūrya wear each a *kiritamukuta*, while the head of Śiva wears a *jatamukuta*. The

halo is flanked on the right and left respectively by four-armed Brahmā and four-armed Śiva each seated in *lalitasana* and is surmounted by four-armed Vishnu seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*. The image is flanked on either side by a rampant *vyala*, a bull-headed deity and a male devotee. Of the latter two each stands in *tribhanga* in *anjalimudra*. It is one of the rare sculptures and is datable to C.11th century A.D.

15. An image of three-headed and four-armed Brahmā standing in *samabhanga*. All hands are broken. It is made of sandstone and is datable to C.11th century A.D.
16. Four-armed Śiva standing in *samabhanga*. and carrying *trisula* and *sarpa* in his upper right and left hands. Both his lower hands have been chopped off. On either side of his head is seen seated Brahmā and Vishnu. He is flanked on either side by an attendant.
17. An image of four-armed Mahishamardini Durgā carrying broken, *trisula*, *khadga*, *khetaka* and holding the demon in human form by his hair. The demon is seen emerging out of his buffalo body.
18. Lakshmī-Nārāyaṇa seated on Garuḍa. On the top of the slab is depicted Narasimha.
19. Four-armed Vishṇu standing in *samabhanga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamala*, *gada*, *chakra* and broken. On either side of his head are depicted seated Brahmā and Śiva.
20. Stone-Slab depicting the ten incarnations of Vishṇu on the *parikara* and four-armed Vishnu as the main or central figure. Vishnu stands in *samabhanga* and carries broken, *gada*, *chakra* and *sankha*. There is an oval halo behind his head. The halo is flanked on the right by seated Brahmā and on the left by seated Śiva.
21. Four-armed Ardhanārīśvara standing in *tribhanga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamala*, broken, broken and broken. There is an oval halo behind his head. The halo is flanked on the right by seated Kārttikeya and on the left by seated Gaṇeśa. The *parikaras* are decorated with *vyalas*. He is flanked on the right by a male attendant and on the left by a female attendant. The mount bull is shown on his right.
22. A stone slab depicting three of the nine *grahas*. Each *graha* is bearded and carries *abhaya* and *kalasa*.
23. A four-armed flying bhūta.
24. An image of Nṛī-varāha partly buried in the ground. He is in *alidha* pose. His halo is decorated with a lotus. The halo is flanked on the right by seated Brahma and on the left by seated Śiva. The goddess Prithvi is seen seated above his left folded hand.

On the top of the slab are depicted two flying *vidyadhara*s each supporting a *mukuta*. Above the head of Varāha is a lotus-parasol.

25. An image of eight-armed dancing Durgā carrying *padma*, *trisula*, *damaru*, *sarpa*, *sarpa*, *khatvanga*, *nrityamudra* and broken. On either side of her head is seen a seated four-armed goddess, that on the left being Pārvatī. On the top is seen a two-armed seated female deity, holding a *kalasa* in her left hand. She is flanked on either side by a flying *vidyadhara* carrying a garland.
26. An image of four-armed Vishṇu carrying *gadā* and *chakra* in his upper two hands. There is an oval halo behind his head. Four-armed seated Brahmā and four-armed seated Śiva are seen on the right and left of his head respectively.
27. Mother and child. The mother is lying and the child is sucking her breast.
28. An image of Yajña-varāha i.e. Varāha in purely zoomorphic form. His body is carved with multiple figures of gods and goddesses.
29. A ceiling stone slab decorated with *kola* and *gajatalu* courses.
30. A ceiling stone slab decorated with full-blown lotus.
31. An image of seated Umā-Maheśvara. The mounts bull and lion are depicted below.
32. Ten-armed Pārvatī standing in *tribhanga*.
33. A carved pillar decorated with a standing *apsaras*.
34. A carved pillar decorated with a standing *apsaras*.
35. A carved pillar decorated with a standing *apsaras*.
36. A rampant *vyala*.
37. A two-armed female deity standing in *tribhanga*. Both her hands are broken.
38. A two-armed *dvarapala* standing in *tribhanga*. His right hand is lost and his left hand is in *kati*. He wears a bejewelled *mukuta* and ornamented drapery.
39. A male attendant carrying *chauri* in his left hand. He wears a bejewelled *mukuta*.
40. A stone slab carved with a niche containing an image of four-armed Vishṇu seated on Garuḍa.
41. A *vyala* figure.
42. Bust of four-armed Vishṇu carrying a *chakra* in his upper left hand.

43. Umā-maheśvara seated on a bull.
44. A *dvarapala* standing in *tribhanga*.
45. A *dvarapala* standing in *tribhanga*.
46. A three-headed male deity (Vishnu) standing in *samabhanga*. All hands are broken. The circular halo behind his head is flanked on the right by seated Brahmā and on the left by seated Śiva. The image probably represents Vaikuṅṭha form of Vishṇu.
47. A seated Nandī.
48. A rampant vyāla.
49. A rampant vyāla.
50. An *apsaras* standing in *tribhanga*. Her hands are lost.
51. A fragmentary pillar carved with an *apsaras* in front.

Jaina Remains.

There are numerous Jaina sculptures in the village, which had a few Jaina temples. The ruins of these temples can still be seen in and around the village. Most of these temples and sculptures belong to C.11th century A.D. The following Jaina remains may be noticed here.

Bank of River Somavati

On the bank of river Somevatī is lying an image of a headless Jaina Tirthankara seated in *dhyanamudra*. Both his hands are lost. He is flanked on either side by a male *chauri*-bearer. The image is made of white sandstone.

Sitalamata temple : The following Jaina remains can be seen among the Hindu remains fixed in the platform of this temple:

1. A Tirthankara seated on a lion-throne in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
2. Pārśvanātha seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*..
3. A stone-slab carved with a standing image of twenty-armed Chakreśvarī yakshī. She wears a *karandamukuta*. The halo behind her head is flanked on either side by a flying *Vdiyadhara* couple. On the top of the slab are shown five seated Jinas. She carries *chakra*, *khadga*, and *khataka* in her extant hands.

4. Two Jinas each standing in *kayotsargamudra*.
5. Four-armed Ambikā seated in *lalitasana*. She holds a mango-bunch in her lower right hand. The child held by her in her lower left hand is lost.
6. A standing Jaina goddess. Above her head are shown three seated Jinas.
7. A Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
8. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
9. A tirthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
10. A stone slab depicting standing Dharaṇendra and Padmāvati. Four Jinas are depicted on the top of the slab.
11. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.

Jaina sculptures lying near Bhavani Temple

These Jaina sculptures (Plate ?, Fig. 5) are lying on the site of a medieval Jaina temple of which only the platform has survived.

1. A colossal image of a Jaina Tīrthankara (Plate ?, Fig. 6) standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga mudra*. There is a circular halo behind his head. He is flanked on the right by Indra and on the left by Upendra both depicted as *chauri*-bearers. There are oval halos behind the heads of Indra and Upendra who wear bejewelled drapery. The fingers of both the hands of the Tīrthankara are broken. The lower portion of the image of Tīrthankara and Indra are partly buried in the earth. A ceiling stone-slab decorated with a lotus having a pendant is also lying buried near this image. A stone slab depicting a frieze of *kirttimukhas* is also lying nearby.
2. A loose sculpture of a Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra* is lying near the platform of the Jaina temple referred to above. He is seated on a *simhasana* and is flanked on either side by a *chauri*-bearer. The sculpture is very much mutilated.
3. Four-armed Chakreśvarī seated in *lalitasana* in a niche and carrying *varada*, *chakra*, *chakra* and *matulunga*.

Jaina sculptures lying in the Ram Singh Bada

1. A stone slab depicting three arches each containing a Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*. The image is kept on a platform inside the *bada*.

2. A stone slab depicting Tīrthaṅkara Sambhavanātha standing in *kayotsarga* and flanked on either side by a male *chauri*-bearer. Only his legs below the knees have survived. The emblem horse is depicted on the pedestal.
3. Simhāsana of a Jaina Tīrthankara image.
4. An image of a Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*. Only the lower portion of this image has survived.

The sculptures described above mark the site of a Jaina temple.

Jaina sculpture in the Rama Mandir outside village

1. Pārśvanātha seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra* on a *simhasana*. There is serpent-canopy above his head. He is flanked on either side by an attendant carrying a *chauri*-bearer. The serpent-canopy is flanked on either side by a standing elephant and is surmounted by a male blowing a conch and three Jinas each seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.

Jaina sculptures in the Open Air Museum

1. Head of Jaina Tīrthankara.
2. Head of a Jaina Tīrthankara.
3. A stone-slab carved with a *pancharatha sikhara* and two Jinas, one standing in *kayotsarga* and the other seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
4. Bust of a Tīrthankara image.
5. Stone-slab carved with two images of Gomukha Yaksha each standing in *samabhanga* and having an elaborate *prabhavali* around his head.
6. Four-armed Yakshī seated in *lalitasana* on a lotus. All her hands are lost. Her halo is decorated with lotus-petals and is flanked on either side by a flying *vidyadhara* couple carrying a garland.
7. A Tīrthankara standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*. Both his hands have been chopped off.
8. A Tīrthankara standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*. The halo behind his head is decorated with lotus-petals and is flanked on either side by a flying *vidyadhara* carrying a garland.

9. A niche containing image of the parents of Tīrthankara seated in *lalitasana*. The mother holds a child. To the right of the niche is depicted another image of Tīrthankara standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*.
10. Tīrthankara standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*. There is a circular lotus-halo behind his head.
11. Tīrthankara standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*. There is a lotus-halo behind his head.
12. Tīrthankara standing in *kayotsarga* in a niche.
13. Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
14. Two Tīrthankaras each standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*.
15. Mother and child. The mother is lying and the child in sucking her breasts.
16. Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
17. Four-armed Ambikā seated in *lalitasana* on a lotus. Her head and both hands are broken. The mount lion is depicted below.
18. A niche containing an image of a Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*. His head is flanked on either side by flying *vidyadhara* carrying a garland.
19. Lintel of the sanctum door-way. It is carved with two rows of sculptures. The upper row depicts eight Tīrthankaras each seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*. The lower row portrays eight seated Mothers. On the *lalatabimba* is shown a Tīrthankara standing in *khadgasana* in *kayotsarga*.
20. Two-armed standing Jaina Yakshī.
21. A Jaina Yaksha standing in *tribhanga* and carrying *kati*. broken, *pustaka* and *pakshi*. He wears a bejewelled *mukuta* and drapery.
22. Parents of Jaina Tīrthankara, each seated in *lalitasana*. The head of the father is lost. In between is depicted a figure in *anjalimudra*.
23. Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
24. Yakshī Ambikā seated in *lalitasana* under a mango tree. Her right hands are broken. She holds a child by her left hand. Five Jinas, each seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra* are shown on the top.
25. Two-armed female deity standing in *tribhanga*. Both her hands are broken.

26. A Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
27. A stone-slab depicting two Tīrthankaras each standing in *kayotsarga*.
28. A Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
29. Pārśvanātha standing in *kayotsarga*.
30. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
31. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
32. A Jina standing *kayotsarga* in a niche.
33. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
34. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
35. The parents of a Tīrthankara each standing in *tribhanga*.
36. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga* and flanked on either side by a *chauri*-bearer.
37. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
38. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
39. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
40. Four-armed Chakrēśvarī Yakshī seated in *lalitasana* on Garuḍa. All hands except the lowest pair holding *chakra* and waterpot mutilated. On the right of her head is seen a flying *vidyadhara* carrying a garland.
41. Seated Ambikā Yakshī. Her breasts and the child held by her in her left hand have been mutilated.
42. Lower portion of an image of Ambikā Yakshī seated in *lalitasana* on a lion carved below.
43. Pārśvanātha seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
44. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
45. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
46. Four-armed Jaina Yaksha standing in *tribhanga*. He holds a lotus and *kati* in his upper and lower left hands respectively.
47. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*. He is surmounted by another Jina seated in

padmasana in *dhyanamudra* and a shrine with a *sikhara*. The right portion of the *parikara* is decorated with *vyalamukhas* and a *vyala*.

48. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*. He is surmounted by another Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra* and a shrine with *sikhara*. The left portion of the *parikara* is decorated with *vyalamukha*, *vyala* and *vyalamukha*.
49. A niche containing an image of a Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
50. Torso of a Jina standing is *kayotsarga*.
51. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
52. A Tīrthankara seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
53. A colossal image of Ādinātha standing in *kayotsarga*. The locks of his hair are seen falling on his shoulders. There is a lotus-halo behind his head. The fingers of his hands are mutilated. On his right is depicted Ambikā Yakshī seated in *lalitasana* and holding a child. On his left is portrayed Yakshī Chakreśvarī seated in *lalitasana* and holding *chakras* in her hands.
54. Four-armed Jaina Yaksha standing in *tribhanga*. All his hands are broken off.
55. A female deity with a serpent-canopy above her hand.
56. A Jina seated in *padmasana* in *dhyanamudra*.
57. A Jina standing in *kayotsarga*.
58. Pedestal of an image of Ādinātha depicting Gomukha Yaksha and Ambikā Yakshī.

It may be said in conclusion that Gandharvapuri was an important centre of Paramara art during the medieval period. Hinduism and Jainism both flourished side by side at the place and their votaries had a spirit of religious tolerance. Gandharvapuri has yielded some of the rare composite images such as Pitāmaha-Harihara-Hiraṇyagarbha, Ardhanārīśvara and Harihara. It proves that a spirit of synthesis was prevalent among the various sects.

The sculptural and architectural remains testify to the fact that there existed a number of Hindu and Jaina temples at the site which collapsed at a later date. The colossal images of Jaina Tīrthankaras testify to the existence of magnificent Jaina temples at the site. The discovery of the images of Jaina Tīrthankaras both in seated and standing postures, of the Jaina Yakshas and Yakshis and parents of Tīrthankaras proves that the place was an important religious seat of the Jainas during the Paramara period.

The architects and sculptors of Gandharvapuri have faithfully followed the canons of *silpa* texts in carving out images of various sects. Like other centres of Paramara art such as those of Dhar, Ujjain, Daśapura and Hinglajgarh, Gandharvapuri was also famous for its temples and sculptures.

NOTES :

- 1 Patil, D R, *The descriptive and classified list of ancient monuments in Madhya Bharat*, Gwalior, 1952, pp. 42 - 43.
- 2 Annual Administration Report, Archeological Department, Gwalior State, 1942 - 46, pp. 22-23, 1917 - 18.
- 3 Ghosh, A. (Ed). *Indian Archaeology - 1963-64, A Review*, New Delhi, 1967, p. 87.
- 4 Ghosh A (Ed), *Jaina Art and Architecture*, Vol.I, New Delhi, 1974, pp. 169 - 70, pl. 98B, Vol. II pl. 183 A.
- 5 Samarpita Jivana, *Pandit Satyandhar Kumarji Sethi Abhiandana Grantha*, Jaipur, 1983, pp. 16-17.

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- Figs. 1-2 Gandhawal. Gandharvasena Temple
- Fig. 3 Gandhawal. Hindu and Jaina images collected in the local open air museum.
- Fig. 4 Gandhawal. Pitamaha - Harihara - Hiranyagarbha. C. 11th century A.D.
- Fig. 5 Gandhwal. Group of Jaina figures. C. 11th century A.D.
- Fig. 6 Gandhawal. Colossal standing Jina. C. 11th century A.D.

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